

PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF MANIPULATION AND INFORMATION SECURITY PROBLEMS

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Abstract: In this scientific work, the processes of manipulation in today's developed information society are extensively analyzed. Interrelationship of manipulation with the concepts of information and information security is revealed. At the same time, the characteristics of manipulation processes as an informational tool are analyzed from other phenomena.

Keywords:

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INTRODUCTION

One of the problems facing mankind is the problem of providing security. Therefore, in learning this problem, it is important to learn manipulation problems. Manipulation processes are very important in the development of the information society and are considered to be of particular importance in ensuring people's safety in information sources. That's why this problem today demands that all branches be integrated and find their own solution.

METHODS

The systematic-structural approach based on objectivity, universality, concreteness, logical, and historical dialectical principles was used in the research. This makes it possible to see the concepts of manipulation and information as a whole system of human society.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Today, the development of the society and the states ensures the strengthening of mutual relations between them. On the one hand, they consider favorable conditions in their environment, but on the other hand, they create new problems in their environment. Therefore, the problem that is considered one of the most important problems today is the problem of information security.

By studying the problem of information security, we will be able to study the problem of information manipulation in every detail. This is the first time that the information is analyzed in relation to the social psychological situation. At the same time, nowadays information is being used to change and manipulate people's

psychology based on influencing their psychology. Therefore, manipulation processes are of particular importance in the problem of information security.

Since the middle of the 20th century, the problem of manipulation has become one of the relevant problems of various modern sciences. Initially, the problem of manipulation was analyzed by the sciences that study social relations (sociology, psychology, political science, etc.), later it became the object of study of other sciences, and the sciences began to analyze this phenomenon in detail.[1] Over the years, manipulation has become a problem of scientific research in philosophy, sociology, politics, psychology, journalism and cybernetics. Each subject of science has learned specifics, signs, tools, methods and methods of manipulation, coming from its subject.

The word "manipulation" itself comes from the Latin word "manipulus" (manus - hand and ple - filling) and means to take control of objects aimed at a specific purpose. If we focus on the history of the term "manipulation", then in ancient Rome it was defined as a group of soldiers who obeyed and obeyed all the orders given by the commanders without question. And in the same line, the problem of manipulating the mind of a person from a philosophical point of view was also started by the modern philosophers. However, the concept of manipulation appeared in science after some time. According to the opinion of the modern Greek philosopher Plato, manipulation is a tool that allows a person to freely submit and control his thoughts without physical coercion. It relates to the art of manipulating manipulation. It is said that the art of Isendiriv controls people voluntarily, not by force. Despite the fact that the problem of manipulation has been studied for a long time, there are no definitive definitions of the concept of manipulation, there is a plurality of opinions on this.

Learning the phenomenon of manipulation is becoming more and more important in the development of modern society. When learning the concept of manipulation, some scientists pay attention to its hidden nature and influence on the mental structure of objects of manipulation. As objects of manipulative influence, society as a whole, starting with an individual, is considered.

One of the conditions of manipulation is a certain mental state of the object of manipulation, which is necessary for the manipulator. The manipulation structure includes four elements in its work:

1. Object. In the process of manipulation, passively accepting the effects.
2. Subject. A manipulator is a person who creates an effect to achieve a favorable result for himself.
3. Subject. opinions, attitudes, desires, goals, which can be changed or can be changed completely during the process of manipulation.
4. Result. A set of goals achieved after the manipulation process is completed.

The most important signs of manipulation include the following: The object of manipulation did not know the effect shown to him, this is related to hiding the true goals of the manipulator; The manipulator affects not only the consciousness, but also the unconscious (instincts, feelings, needs); The manipulator controls the relationship of the object of manipulation to the objects and phenomena of the world moving in a certain direction; The manipulator controls the thoughts, feelings, behaviors, attitudes and relationships of the object of manipulation; The manipulator works by providing information, as a result of this, noticeable changes (disinformation, choices, etc.) occur and causes a special distortion of the facts; Integrational character - related to mutual integration of sciences and theories; Application of specialized knowledge - refers to the acquisition of specific knowledge and skills; Focused on a specific goal - it is created to achieve certain results; Non-violent nature - a given action is carried out without physical coercion in the direction of the given goal.

Studying the many definitions of manipulation, we can mention several ways of showing its differences: the first is a psychological or spiritual effect (psychological understanding); second-hand speech or language effect (linguistic understanding); from the third, the method of management or governance (political understanding); and the fourth is the impact based on attitudes (sociological understanding).

E.Dotsenko made the manipulation into a psychological understanding, and considers the manipulation as "a type of psychological effect, performed skillfully". G.Frank considers that manipulation "is carried out in a covert manner and causes damage to the targeted persons" as a psychological effect. B.Bessonov, N.Obozov, and P.Freire propose to understand the concept of "spiritual influence" in the framework of the psychological understanding of manipulation as "a specific form of spiritual influence, depicted in a hidden, anonymous dominant image." Manipulation can have a political content in the works of political scientists (Y.Ermakov, S.Kara-Murza, E.Sheigal, P.Freire, R.Goodin, R.Lakoff and others).[2] He pays attention to the fact that manipulation is a "ruling way", a "weapon of enslavement", a "hidden use of power". And manipulation is shown in the studies of methods in social psychological fields as "manipulation is a strategy of social behavior for the personal goals of the manipulator, contrary to the personal values of the addressee."

A.Filatov, a well-known scientist, says that the ownership of such ideas, which illuminate the world in an incomplete or distorted way, about the events of human history, is somewhat suggestive of manipulation of the human mind.

S.Kierkegaard considered manipulation to be the act of controlling the mind and will, and they believed that the will gives a person the opportunity to freely

determine his own destiny. The lack of free choice leads to the gradual loss of human dignity (both for oneself and for others). It should be mentioned that freedom is manipulated by the subject instead of the object, and this leads to the gradual disappearance of the concept of "personal self" of the object of manipulation. It is worth mentioning that manipulation is considered as a covert surveillance business, as a tool and process of influencing the spiritual world of the object of covert surveillance.

G.Kolesnikova mentioned two parameters for distinguishing manipulation from all other influences: these are the covertness or hidden nature of the influence and the presence of malicious intentions.

And what the giant G. Simon says about manipulation, the specifics of psychological manipulation related to it are as follows:

- ❖ Concealment of malicious intent and actions. Covertly influencing people's minds when the subjects of manipulation hide their own goals.

- ❖ Choose the most effective method based on the knowledge of the victim. Choose methods based on collecting information about the object in the process of manipulation.

- ❖ Be ready to attack objects of manipulation when necessary. Manipulation is creating a new center by spreading information and preparing to influence them immediately or gradually.

G.Simon shows several methods of manipulation without showing the psychological features of manipulation as follows:

- ❖ The method of using lies - in this method, the truth will be revealed later, when it is too late. And during the conversation, it is guided by the use of falsehood, which is a tool for detection.

- ❖ The method of silent deception is one of the most subtle forms of false information transmission, which promotes manipulation based on hiding the big truth.

- ❖ Distortion method - the manipulative subject does not respond directly to direct questions, and diverts the conversation to other processes to achieve his or her own goals.

- ❖ The method of covert intimidation - the subject of manipulation demands submission to the object of manipulation with the help of covert (intimidation) threats.

- ❖ Method of rationalization - the manipulative subject promotes the manipulation of the human mind by justifying his actions with many reliable arguments.

In recent years, mind manipulation has become an effective method of shaping public opinion. Manipulative influence is considered the most effective form of

influence on the wider society. It refers to covert surveillance, persuasion, coercion, and changing any characteristics of the subject's personality (his mind or actions). That is why this problem does not lose its relevance. Manipulation is "opinion about the events is better than the truth itself". The superiority of artificially created events over real events is important.

Manipulation is a system of influences that requires special knowledge and implements to change the opinion, views, attitude and goals of the person being manipulated.

CONCLUSIONS

Metaphorically speaking, the concept of manipulation is often used equivalent to the psychological effect of inducing people to perform certain actions, changing their psychological descriptions and situations. Manipulation is considered a certain type of social psychological effect, it poisons the minds of people through manipulation, violence, deception and secret actions towards the goal of some subjects.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. Fisenko P.I. Personally-psychological sources of dangers in society and psychological aspects of national-state security. Moscow, 1994.S. 133.
2. Roshchin S.K. Sosnin V.A. Psychological safety: a new approach to the safety of man, society and the state. Moscow - 1995.115
3. Fisenko P.I. General safety theory (relevant methodological and socio-political problems). Moscow. 1994.46
4. Moslou A. Toyard A. Psychologist of Being. N.Y. 1968.